

Test Anxiety and Academic Stress as Predictive Factors of Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State

¹Dr. Chikezie Victoria Chineme & ²Dr. Onukaogu Loveline Ifeoma

¹University of Port Harcourt Demonstration Primary School;

Early Childhood and Primary Education, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State

²Institute of Education University of Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding Authors' Email: ifylove1982@gmail.com; veekychi08@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examined test anxiety and academic stress as predictive factors of examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. The study adopted correlational research design. Two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school students in Isi Local Government Area. The population comprised 13,976 students. The sample size comprised 400 students selected through purposive and simple random sampling technique. The researcher developed a self-structured questionnaire titled "Psychological Factors and Students' Examination Questionnaire" (PFSQ). The PFSQ is divided into three sections, A, B and C. Section A was made up of demographic variables such as name of institution, gender, qualification. Section B and C contained 10 and 10 item statements each to measure psychological factors and examination malpractice. The PFSQ was validated and tested for reliability using test re-test method where copies of the instrument was administered to 30 students who were not part of the study. The reliability indices of PFSQ ($r=0.72$) and EMI ($r=0.90$). Simple linear regression was used to answer research questions 1 to 2 and test the null hypotheses 1 to 2. The analyses of the hypotheses was tested for statistical significance at .05 alpha level. The data analyzed showed that to a very high extent test anxiety significantly predicted examination malpractice among senior secondary school students and to a very high extent academic stress significantly predicted examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the researcher made some appropriate recommendations such as senior secondary school teachers should ensure that students are prepared adequately to face their examinations by covering all the syllabus before the examinations. Also, government should provide learning materials to enhance effective teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Academic Stress, Examination Malpractice, Predictive Factors, Test Anxiety

INTRODUCTION

The menace of examination malpractice is quite old in Nigeria. In the words of Olushola (2016), the brief history of examination malpractice in Nigeria according to historical records is traceable to the year 1914, when there was a leakage of question paper into senior Cambridge Local Examination. Cheating in examination is a manifestation of dishonest attitude. It is a deliberate act of commission made by a candidate, single-handedly or in collaboration with others, to obtain a better grade than he is capable of obtaining, but has also affected the validity of examination results and certificates issued to candidates concerned (Turner, 2018).

Examinations is the main method used in the evaluation of students in Nigeria. The purpose of the national education among others is to improve effective decision making about the learners and in our case those in secondary schools in Nigeria. Cheating in examinations started before the early 70s, the situation became worse in 2011 when mass cheating was first perpetrated in WAEC examination resulting in public outcry on the credibility of examinations then

in Nigeria. In the 1990s, the act became a dangerous epidemic because it spread in a great proportion to every level of the educational institution in the country (Onyibe, Uma & Ibina, 2015). Examination malpractice maybe defined as deliberate wrong doing by the exam takers contrary to the examination rules in which some candidates may get an unfair advantage or disadvantage (Uzoma, Onyia & Ekoh, 2022).

Examination malpractice allow some students to get good results by any fraudulent means and this may encourage mediocrity since those students who got such results by fraudulent means maybe be rated equal to those who really struggled and worked hard on their own to excel. Examination malpractice may also be defined as any form of fraudulent activity by a learner with the mind-set of getting better results than their actual level of intelligence and academics performance elaborates. Examination malpractice as any form of misbehaviour that leads to the alteration of or a tempering with the prescribed ways of conducting examination in any given system. He further said examination malpractice is a punishable

offence which is committed during the process of normal and recognized examination. Examination malpractice as any wrong doing, misconduct, dishonesty or improper practices for personal gains or violation of set rules of conduct during examination (Ugboha & Gungung, 2022).

There has been much outcry on the issue of examination malpractice and the fall of the standard of Education in Nigeria. A lot of questions have been raised as to what factors are responsible for this and what sustains examination malpractice in the education sector from primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education. However, it has been observed that students no longer consider hard work as a prerequisite for success but tend to substitute it with examination malpractice in order to succeed. Parents are not exonerated from the blame of instigating cheating as some parents do all they could to make sure that their children pass examinations. Teachers who are not well equipped in terms of training contribute to examination malpractice in schools. Non-payment of teachers' salary as at when due and grant or allowances might also facilitate examination malpractice on the part of teachers who try hard to make ends meet even out of greed and bribery. Government policies regarding education and politics and employing non-qualified teachers who are relatives of government officials jeopardize the progress of the country's education sector (Ugboha & Gungung, 2022).

Unfortunately, despite students' involvement in examination malpractice in Isu Local government area of Imo State, Nigeria, students' academic achievement in has not significantly improved their academic achievement. And the dwindling performance in the education system over the years has not appreciated to commensurate the sharp practice to gain unmerited grades in the various specified examinations. From the foregoing, it is very clear that the trend is growing downward. This result therefore, bring to focus the need, to investigate the psychological factors that promote examination malpractice and how these problems can be addressed among secondary school students in Isu Local government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Psychological factors refer to one's psychological dispositions which are capable of affecting development, behaviour and interaction with the environment. Psychological factors influence human reasoning and behaviour, emotions, and cognitive abilities in classroom engagement. Teachers should motivate students to learn effectively as this will promote self-efficacy and resilience that is needed to prepare for external examinations. Psychological factors can be positive, such as happiness, affect, and vitality, or negative, such as anxiety, perceived stress, and depressive symptoms. These can also be split to distinguish between trait and state aspects. Personality traits, depressive factors, well-being, quality of life, and the impact of significant life events and trauma are

less likely to fluctuate on a day to day basis (i.e., more trait-like or stable variables), whereas anxiety, perceived stress, mood, affect, happiness, and vitality are more unstable i.e., more state-like (Okafor, Nonye & Mbachu, 2024).

Test anxiety is a variable to be investigated in this study. Most students engage in examination due to fear of failing and the outcome that comes with failing. Thus they are willing to do anything within their powers to avoid failure. Test anxiety refer to feelings of distress that are associated with taking tests or examination. It is a psychological matter that if not handle adequately will result in sickness. Some persons refers to it as examination fever (Turner, 2018).

Stress, another core psychological factor, remains a pervasive challenge in contemporary society. Stress is usually an unpleasant feeling especially when situational demands is beyond the capacity of the person (Uzoeshi, 2012). Uzoeshi (2017) defined stress as any demand that affects an individual's body mechanism and force him to take extra step in order to restore or maintain the equilibrium. Academic stress refers to work overload given to students. Some teachers are found given too much homework and too difficult examinations, as cheating during examination becomes the option.

Examination malpractice takes different forms such as; Impersonation, use of mobile phones during examinations, external assistance, inscription, irregular activities inside and outside the examination halls, sorting, exam paper leakages, etc. the factors responsible for examination malpractice among senior secondary school students include lack of confidence by students which may be due to adequate preparation, examination anxiety, and academic stress. Teacher factors is significantly related to examination malpractice. When teachers failed to prepare their students by not completing the scheme of work termly, students' ability to pass their exams can be jeopardized by poor teaching methods. School facilities can also hinder effective teaching and learning processes as such the government must wakeup to her responsibilities (Ofuonyebuzor & Obingba, 2025). Parental influence is another factor responsible for examination malpractice. Most parents want their children to pass out of school with very high grades by all means. Some parents are ready to offer money to the school authority to assist their children during examination (Onyibe, Uma & Ibina, 2015).

Theoretical Background of the Study

This study was anchored on Social Learning Theory, as proposed by Albert Bandura.

Social Learning Theory (Albert Bandura in 1986)

The study was anchored on Social Learning Theory, developed by Albert Bandura in 1986. The theory opined that people learn behaviours, attitudes, and emotional reactions through observing others within a social context. Psychological variables factors play a

critical role in this learning process. According to Bandura, individuals, particularly students, observe the behaviors of their peers, family members, and authority figures. For instance, a student who observes peers receiving praise or higher social status for academic success may be motivated to emulate those behaviours to gain similar rewards. This observational learning process is influenced by the perceived similarity and status of the model, the observed consequences of the behavior, and the student's own expectations and beliefs about the outcomes. If cheating is normalized and seemingly goes unpunished within a peer group, a student may adopt this behavior to conform to group norms. Bandura's theory highlighted the complex interplay of these psychosocial variables, demonstrating how social environments and cognitive processes jointly shape people behavior.

Empirical evidence relating the variables used in this study were carried out. Segun (2021) examined Age, sex and test anxiety as predictors to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Akoko South West Local Government Area in Ondo State, Nigeria. The finding of the study revealed that there was a significant positive relationship between test anxiety and examination malpractice among students. The study found that age and sex significantly predicted examination malpractice. Eremie et al. (2020) carried out a study on cognitive test anxiety and examination malpractices among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. It was found that there is a significant relationship between excessive trembling, feeling of hopelessness, low self-esteem, affective tension and examination malpractices among secondary school students in Rivers State. It was concluded that we live in a test taking society and that when students are anxious before and during tests, cognitive test anxiety has a significant and effective impact on their involvement in examination malpractice which invariably leads to poor academic performance. Prabu (2015) also did another study on stress and examination malpractice among higher school students in China. The study was aimed at finding out what caused unpleasant emotions like fear in students during examination. The study found out that high school students do have moderate and higher level of stress which is responsible for examination malpractices.

Statement of Problem

Examination malpractice in the Nigeria education system has assumed varied levels in recent times. Amongst the students, attending classes, reading and doing ones' assignment and other forms of hard work in school have been sacrificed on the altar of malpractice and sharp practice just to pass examination. In our Primary, post- primary and tertiary institutions, pupils and students alike engage in unethical practices during examination. Some practices commonly found during examination include

but not limited to sorting, teachers' sale of examination paper before the date of the examination, copying and impersonation.

Examination malpractice is quite disheartening considering the prominence assumed by the act in the school system. The author pointed out that the phenomenon has become a source of concern to stakeholders since almost every person in one way or the other contributes to examination malpractice. This is a very dangerous condition in our educational system that calls for urgent attention. Some factors that promote examination malpractices among students include fear of failure, school dropout, stigmatization, over-emphasizes on paper certificates, poverty, High parental expectations, inadequate instructional materials, poor teaching methods, poor teachers' quality, under-achievement, etc. Much has not been identified of the psychological factors affecting students which has created a gap in previous studies. It is against this backdrop that the researcher seek to investigate the psychosocial variables and examination malprice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim and objectives of this study is to examined test anxiety and academic stress as predictive factors of examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. Find out the extent to which test anxiety predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school Students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria.
2. Determine the extent to which academic stress predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school Students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does test anxiety predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school Students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does academic stress predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school Students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are formulated to guide the study in order to arrive at a valid conclusion. They are stated as follows:

1. Test anxiety does not significantly predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria
2. Academic stress does not significantly predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the correlational research design. This is because the researcher is interested in finding out how social variables predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. Ogidi (2018) defined correlation as that statistical tool used to determine the level of relationship between two variables, and among three or more variables. Correlational studies are research concerned with determining the relationship between two or more variables and also used in testing hypothesis of significance. The population of the study consisted of all the senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State which comprised 13,976 students (source: planning research and statistics, UBE, Board, Imo State, 2024). The purposive random sampling technique was used to select the respondents from the schools within the area. There are twenty-five (20) senior secondary schools in the study area. Twenty (20) students was selected from each school to give equal opportunity to the schools and make better generalizations of the findings of the study.

The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Psychological Factors and Students’ Examination Malpractice Questionnaire” (PFSEMQ). Section A comprised demographic data such as gender, age, class, school type and parents’ socio-economic background. Section B is divided into two; “Psychological Factors Questionnaire” (PFQ) and “Examination Malpractice

Inventory” (EMI), consisted of 20 items and 10 items respectively that used to generate responses to measure psychological factors and examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State. It was responded to on a four (4) point modified Likert-type rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. The criterion mean of 2.5 was used to judge the level of acceptance.

The reliability of the instruments was determined through the Cronbach Alpha method. Copies of the instrument were administered to 30 secondary school students randomly selected who were not part of the study population. The scores obtained were subjected to Cronbach Alpha analysis and a reliability indices obtained are PVSEMQ ($\alpha=0.89$) and EMI ($\alpha=0.83$). The collected data were analysed using simple linear regression to answer the research questions and to test all the hypotheses. The results of the analysis of the hypotheses will be tested for significance at the 0.05 level.

RESULT

Research Question One: To what extent does test anxiety predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis One: Test anxiety does not significantly predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria

Table 1a: Linear Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Test Anxiety Predicts Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.811 ^a	0.658	0.657	4.789

a. Predictors: (Constant), Test Anxiety
 b. Dependent Variable: Examination Malpractice

Table 1b: Regression Coefficients of the Relationship between Test Anxiety and Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26.931	1.104		24.402	0.000
	Test Anxiety	2.538	0.092	0.811	27.610	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Substance Abuse

Table 1c: ANOVA Analysis of the Significance of Test Anxiety and Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17485.451	1	17485.451	762.308	.000 ^b
	Residual	9106.193	397	22.938		
	Total	26591.644	398			

a. Dependent Variable: Examination Malpractice

b. Predictors: (Constant), Test Anxiety

Table 1a shows the linear relationship between test anxiety and examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. As such, the answer to research question one is that to a high extent test anxiety predicts examination of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State is very high ($R = 0.811$).

The test to hypothesis one in Table 1b and Table 1c revealed the linear relationship between test anxiety and examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State ($F_1 = 762.308$, $df = 397$, $p < 0.05$). The implication of this result is that to a very high extent

significantly test anxiety predicts examination of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. Thus, hence null hypothesis one is rejected at the 0.05 significance level.

Research Question Two: To what extent does academic stress predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school Students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis Two: Academic stress does not significantly predict examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria

Table 2a: Linear Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Academic Stress Predicts Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.744 ^a	0.553	0.552	5.470

a. Predictors: (Constant), Academic Stress

b. Dependent Variable: Examination Malpractice

Table 2b: Regression Coefficients of the Relationship between Academic Stress and Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	31.935	1.149		27.802	0.000
	Stress	2.149	0.097	0.744	22.176	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Stress

Table 2c: ANOVA Analysis of the Significance of Academic Stress and Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14713.912	1	14713.912	491.796	0.000 ^b
	Residual	11877.732	397	29.919		
	Total	26591.644	398			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Stress

b. Predictors: (Constant), Examination Malpractice

Table 2a shows the linear relationship between academic stress and examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. As such, the answer to research question two is that to a high academic extent stress predicts examination of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State is very high ($R = 0.744$).

The test to hypothesis two in Table 2b and Table 2c revealed the linear relationship between academic

stress and examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State ($F_1 = 491.796$, $df = 397$, $p < 0.05$). The implication of this result is that to a very high extent significantly academic stress predicts examination of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. Thus, hence null hypothesis two is rejected at the 0.05 significance level.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated psychosocial variables and examination malpractice among junior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. The discussion of the various findings is presented under the following sub-headings:

Test Anxiety and Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State

The Adjusted R-square value of .657 in part A of Table 1 showed a 65.8% contribution of test anxiety towards examination malpractice of students. The regression equation ($y = 26.931 + 2.538x$) shows that an increase in test anxiety of students might lead to a concurrent increase in Examination Malpractice of students. Also, part B of the Table 1b shows that linear regression analysis on the extent to which test anxiety predicts examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State might be described as very high and positive (Beta .811). Table 1c shows the result of the F-statistic indicating that text anxiety significantly predicts examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State ($F_{1, .397} = 762.308, p < .05$). The null hypothesis is rejected at .05 Alpha level of significance.

The finding of this study is supported by the study of Segun (2021) who examined Age, sex and test anxiety as predictors to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Akoko South West Local Government Area in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study found that there was a significant positive relationship between test anxiety and examination malpractice among students. The study found that age and sex significantly predicted examination malpractice. Also, the finding of this present study is in agreement with the finding of Eremie et al. (2020) that we live in a test taking society and that when students are anxious before and during tests, cognitive test anxiety has a significant and effective impact on their involvement in examination malpractice which invariably leads to poor academic performance.

This finding is not surprising because students who are not adequately prepared by their teachers will become anxious which negatively affect their performance. The only way out is to copy from every available material just to pass the examination.

Academic Stress and Examination Malpractice among Senior Secondary School Students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State

The Adjusted R-square value of .552 in part A of Table 2 showed a 55.3% contribution of test anxiety towards examination malpractice of students. The regression equation ($y = 31.935 + 2.149x$) shows that an increase in academic stress of students might lead to a concurrent increase in Examination Malpractice of students. Also, part B of the Table 2b shows that linear

regression analysis on the extent to which stress predicts examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State might be described as very high and positive (Beta .744). Table 2c shows the result of the F-statistic indicating that academic stress significantly predicts examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State ($F_{1, .397} = 491.796, p < .05$). The null hypothesis is rejected at .05 Alpha level of significance.

This finding is consistent with the study carried out by Kumari and Jain (2014) who found that many students are afraid of examination leading to examination stress and examination malpractices. They found a positive correlation between examination stress and examination malpractice among secondary school students. The present finding is collaborated with the finding of Prabu (2015) who found out that high school students do have moderate and higher level of stress which is responsible for examination malpractices. The male students' academic stress are higher than the female students from the private school are having low stress. Many factors are responsible for this such as parental level of education, teaching methods/teaching facilities and teachers' attitude towards students.

The finding of this study is not surprising because academic work overload can negatively affect the junior secondary school students. Too much notes for students to copy without adequate explanation by the teachers can be a great challenge. Also, when the school time table is loaded such that students do not have time to play, this can affect their level of assimilation.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated psychological factors and examination malpractice among senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area, Imo State. However, the findings of the study showed that test anxiety positively and significantly predicts examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State, that academic stress positively and significantly predicts examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State, that test anxiety positively and significantly predicts examination malpractice of senior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State, and that academic stress positively and significantly predicts examination malpractice of junior secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State.

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that test anxiety and academic stress are very influential factors in predicting examination malpractice among senior secondary school students

in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State. Thus, for effective prevention and intervention strategies, it is important to focus on addressing these factors. This suggests that interventions focusing on improving teachers' attitude to work, school administration to ensure that teachers teach learning contents effectively, ensure that students are not given too much workload as ways to reduce the incidence of examination malpractice among students in this region. Teachers and parents must work together to create a supportive and nurturing environment for students, as well as provide education and resources on coping mechanisms for stress and building self-esteem.

Implications of the Study for Counselling

The following are the counselling implications of the study:

1. Counsellors should be aware of the influence of psychological factors on examination malpractice and incorporate education during guidance programmes and group counselling sessions with teachers, parents and students. This approach can help students understand the negative implications on examination malpractice.
2. Counsellors working with secondary school students in Isu Local Government Area of Imo State should consider addressing test anxiety, stress and peer pressure issues among students, and providing interventions for examination malpractice. Additionally, incorporating strategies to help students develop healthier coping mechanisms on test anxiety, stress and decision-making skills may negative peer group pressure will be beneficial in reducing the incidence of examination malpractice.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the findings, discussion and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers should prepare students adequately for examination by covering their course work as this will reduce the anxiety of failing in examination. Teaching should be made simpler through the use of different teaching methods.
2. School authorities should ensure that school time table is not overloaded. Even during the examinations, the time table should be such that allow for spacing of subjects to able students to read their textbooks and prepare effectively before their examination.

References

Akram, M. & Khan, M.I. (2012). Assessment of academic stress and problem solving among senior secondary school students. *Social Science International*, 28(2), 265.

Amadi, E. C. & Opuiyo, A. R. (2018). Examination malpractice among Nigeria university students: A review. *International Journal of Innovative Legal and Political Studies*, 6(1), 13-17.

Bedewey, D. & Gabriel, A. (2017). Examining perceptions of academic stress and its sources among secondary school students: The perception of academic stress scale. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 1(15), 65-75.

Ikechukwu, L. C., Oti, C. J., Okeke, F. C. & Usulor, J. (2019). Factors responsible for examination malpractice among secondary school students in christian religious education. *International Business Management*, 13(16), 220-227.

Ofuonyebuzor, P. A. & Obimgba, G. N. (2015). Menace of examination malpractice: private vs public schools in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Information System Research (IJASIR)*, 9(4), 72-76.

Ogonda, M. P., Allwell, E. N. & Maclean, O. (2022). Sources of stress among secondary school students in Rivers State in post covid-19 era. *Rivers State Counselling Association of Nigeria Journal (RIVCASSON)*, 5(2), 54-63.

Okafor, N. C., Nonye, N. N. & Mbachu, C. U. (2024). Causes and effects of examination anxiety on learning among students: Implications for counselling. *The Anambra Counsellors*, 1(2), 47-55.

Onyibe, C. O., Uma, U. U. & Ibina, E. (2015). Examination malpractice in Nigeria: Causes and effects on national development. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(26), 12-17.

Selye, H. (1950). Stress and the general adaptation syndrome. *British Medical Journal*, 1(4667), 1383.

Turner, T. (2018). Correlate of examination malpractice and academic performance of secondary schools in Obio/Akpor and Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Entrepreneurship Development*, 1(1), 102-113.

Ugboha, G. O. & Gungung, M. D. (2022). Examination malpractice in Nigeria educational system: origin, types, causes, effects and implication for counselling.

- Prestige Journal of Counselling Psychology*, 5(1), 186-194.
- Uzoeshi, K. C. (2012). *Everyday stress and its management*. Zetus Integrated Concepts.
- Uzoma, F. C., Onyia, C. & Ekoh, L. A (2022). Effect of examination malpractice on national development of Nigeria: Perceived causes and forms. *International Digital OrganiZation for Scientific Research. Journal of Banking Economics and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 1-14.